

Comparative Efficacy of Serratus Anterior Plane Block (SAPB) and Fentanyl for Postoperative Pain Management and Stress Response in Patients undergoing Minimally Invasive Cardiac Surgery (MICS)

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Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 26-06-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Through the facilitation of early extubation and optimum pain management, fast tracking plays a key role in lowering perioperative morbidity and length of hospital stay following surgery. Enhancing recovery also greatly benefits from reducing the stress reaction to surgery. A novel method for chest wall analgesia has been described recently: serratus anterior plane block (SAPB). To determine the efficacy of SAPB analgesia for minimally invasive cardiac surgery (MICS), further information is needed.

Aim and objectives: The purpose of the research was to evaluate the safety and effectiveness of SAPB guided by ultrasonography in comparison to fentanyl for the management of post-thoracotomy pain and stress in patients receiving MICS. Setting and Design: This was a prospective, observational, and comparative research that was time-framed.

Materials and Methods: Two groups were randomly allocated to patients receiving MICS for coronary artery bypass grafting while under general anaesthesia. Patients in the SAPB group (Group A) received 0.2% of 20 ml ropivacaine before having a catheter inserted for ongoing infiltration at the conclusion of the surgery. Patients in the fentanyl group (Group B) received fentanyl intravenously as postoperative analgesics. The main result assessed how much pain was evaluated using the visual analogue scale (VAS) and how much stress response was quantified using cortisol levels in both groups.

Results: In comparison to Group B, Group A's VAS score was considerably lower ($P < 0.0001$). The SAPB group also had decreased cortisol levels. Group A exhibited more stability in hemodynamic measures, including oxygen saturation, pulse rate, diastolic blood pressure, and systolic blood pressure, and required fewer top-up analgesics.

Conclusion: When it came to treating post-thoracotomy pain following MICS, SAPB worked better than fentanyl. The group that took SAPB had reduced cortisol levels.

Keywords: cortisol level; minimally invasive heart surgery; serratus anterior plane block; stress reaction.

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Introduction

Reduced hospital stay and ideal postoperative analgesia are the goals of minimally invasive cardiac surgery (MICS), which allows for early ambulation and rehabilitation.[1] Improving healing requires reducing the stress reaction following surgery. An increasingly standardized, patient-centered approach to opioid sparing analgesia is enhanced recovery after surgery (ERAS).[1,2] The optimal recovery profile is intended to be ensured by using the finest postoperative analgesics.[3] A newly published

method for chest wall analgesia is called serratus anterior plane block (SAPB), which targets the plane above or below the serratus anterior muscle in the mid-axillary line while delivering anaesthesia to dermatomes T2 through T9.[4] During the surgery, local anaesthetics are injected between the chest wall's muscular planes, specifically targeting the lateral cutaneous branches of the intercostal nerves.[4,5] SAPB has demonstrated its effectiveness in the treatment of postoperative pain following thoracoscopy, thoracotomy, breast

surgery, and numerous fractures of the ribs.[4,6,7] There isn't enough information available to determine how effectively SAPB analgesia works for MICS. The results of your study showed how the SAPB affected MICS patients' postoperative analgesia. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the safety and effectiveness of fentanyl versus ultrasound guided SAPB in managing thoracotomy pain and stress response in a patient undergoing MICS. Additionally, we searched for any problems such as respiratory depression, hemodynamic instability, and pain intensity.

Materials and Methods

Included were patients having elective MICS. We eliminated from our research any patients who had speech difficulties or opioid abuse. There were 80 people in the sample. In the research done by Berthoud et al. [8], 46 patients were assigned. In this study, 46% of the patients were involved. Thus, $P = 0.46$ for this investigation. With an 87% power, 80 patients were needed for this investigation. Approximately eighty patients were collected and split into two groups.

The sample size is determined using the formula $n = 4pq/(L^2)$, where $p = 0.46$ (following the research by Berthoud et al.) [8] $q = 1 - p$, $L = \text{Loss \% (Loss of information)}$, and $n = \text{needed sample size}$. The computation is as follows: $P = 0.46$, $q = 1 - P = 1 - 0.46 = 0.54$, $4pq = 4 \times 0.46 \times 0.54 = 0.9936$, $L^2 = 0.0124$, $n = 4pq/(L^2) = 0.9936/0.0124 = 80.13 = 80$. With ethics committee approval, this time-framed comparative observational study was carried out. The patients were divided into two groups, Group A and Group B, each with forty patients, at random. At the conclusion of the procedure in the operating room, the catheter was implanted for a continuous infusion of ropivacaine. Group A (the SAPB group) received a bolus dosage of 0.2% of 20 ml ropivacaine. The fifth rib was found at the mid-axillary line when the patient was supine and tilted laterally. Using a linear probe (10–12 Hz), the serratus anterior, latissimus dorsi, and the intercostal muscles were located in the fourth and fifth intercostal spaces.

The serratus anterior and intercostal muscles were pricked with a 20G 10 cm needle, and the proper plane was determined by feeling the usual saline spread through the plane. After a 0.2% ropivacaine bolus was administered initially, a catheter was implanted to provide for a continuous infusion of the drug during the postoperative period at a rate of 15–20 mg/h via an infusion pump. Intravenous (IV) fentanyl infusion was administered to Group B (fentanyl group) using a continuous infusion pump at a rate of 10–30 mcg/h. Following extubation, both groups were observed for 48 hours at intervals of 15 minutes, 30 minutes, 1, 2, 4, 6, 12, 24, 36, and 48 hours, in that order. Six hours apart, each

patient received IV paracetamol. The VAS score was used to measure the patients' pain, and they were observed for hemodynamic changes 48 hours after surgery. A patient assesses their pain on a simple scale from 0 to 10, with 0 denoting no pain and 10 denoting the greatest possible agony, to determine their VAS score, a unidimensional measure of pain severity.

The first and second postoperative days were used to determine serum cortisol (S. cortisol) levels prior to surgery. Chest X-ray improvement was noticed, incentive spirometry volumes were recorded, and the need for further analgesics were reported. Data was input into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and subjected to statistical analysis using GraphPad Prism version 5 and the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (version 25.0; SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). For numerical variables, the data has been presented as mean and standard deviation (SD), and for categorical variables, as count and percentages. A P-value of less than 0.05 was deemed statistically significant.

Results

In this study, data from eighty individuals were examined. Triple vessel and double vessel coronary artery disease were the primary indications for surgery. Table 1 show that the demographic data for both groups was similar. As shown in Table 2, the mean S. cortisol value on postoperative day 1 (POD1) was greater in the fentanyl group than in the SAPB group. $P = 0.3037$ indicates that the difference was not statistically significant. Table 3 compared the two groups' intensive care unit (ICU) stays, spirometry readings, and pain levels. The fentanyl group had considerably higher VAS scores than the SAPB group, and there was a statistically significant difference in the mean VAS after 15 minutes, 1, 2, 4, 6, 10, 24, and 48 hours after surgery ($P < 0.0001$). At 2, 6, 10, 12, and 48 hours postoperatively, the SAPB group's spirometry mean values were higher; however, this difference in mean was not statistically significant. The SAPB group's ICU stay duration was considerably shorter ($P < 0.0001$).

In the SAPB group, no patient needed to be re-intubated. Conversely, due to hypoxemia, two patients in the fentanyl group needed bi-level positive airway pressure. There was no discernible difference in mean heart rate (HR), systolic blood pressure (SBP), and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) between the two groups when hemodynamic parameters were compared. After surgery, measurements of peripheral capillary oxygen saturation (SpO₂) were taken at 15, 30, 1, 2, 6, 10, 12, 24, and 48 hours. Although the SAPB group's mean SpO₂ was greater, the mean difference was not statistically significant. At different time intervals, there was no statistically significant

difference in the mean partial pressure of oxygen (pO₂) values of the two groups. The fentanyl group had increased partial pressure of carbon dioxide (pCO₂) levels at 2, 18, and 26 hours after surgery. In both groups, the difference in mean was statistically significant at two hours (P = 0.0234) and twenty-six hours (P = 0.0026). After surgery, Group A experienced a lower incidence of basal atelectasis than Group B. On POD1 and POD2, 35% of patients in the fentanyl group had significant basal atelectasis, whereas 65% of patients in the SAPB group had mild basal atelectasis. The remaining 25% of patients had no basal atelectasis. P value was significant statistically. Compared to the 62.5% of patients in the fentanyl group, only 17.5% of patients in the SAPB group had mild basal atelectasis on POD 2.

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Table 1: Demographic profile and preoperative values of the patients

Parameters	SAPB group (mean±SD)	Fentanyl group (mean±SD)	P-value
Age (yrs)	63.271±9.269	60.269±10.879	0.1877
BMI (Kg/m ²)	24.109±1.829	24.841±2.069	0.0974
Pre-op pO ₂ (mmHg)	85.571±9.401	88.439±19.241	0.4003
Surgery duration (h)	3.679±0.659	3.429±0.869	0.1722

Table 2: Comparison of S. cortisol (mcg/dl) in both groups preoperatively and postoperatively

Parameters	SAPB group (mean±SD)	Fentanyl group (mean±SD)	P-value
S.cortisol (preoperative)	14.531±5.601	12.301±6.209	0.0989
S.cortisol (POD1)	24.869±12.031	28.701±20.071	0.3037
S.cortisol (POD2)	21.849±8.501	21.329±7.709	0.7772

Table 3: Comparison of pain scores, spirometry values, and ICU stay between two groups

Parameters	SAPB group (mean±SD)	Fentanyl group (mean±SD)	P-value
VAS score	1.549±1.151	3.419±1.189	<0.0001
Spirometry in ml at 48 h	603.749±172.609	598.709±255.069	0.9184
ICU stay (days)	3.769±1.021	5.049±0.901	<0.0001

Discussion

In patients receiving MICS, we have compared SAPB to fentanyl infusion in our study. In a research by Berthoud et al. [8], 26 patients had persistent wound infiltration and 20 patients receiving MICS got SAPB. After 48 hours, VAS scores showed that patients on SAPB consumed much less morphine and had a lower numerical rating scale (NRS) in the first 48 hours after MICS (P < 0.01). Research by Park et al. [9] and Okmen et al. [6] found that the SAPB group's VAS ratings were considerably lower.

The mean VAS score values in Group A (SAPB group) were 2.52, 2.55, 2.45, 2.25, 2.20, 2.02, 1.80, 1.55, 1.12, and 0.85 at 15 minutes, 1, 2, 4, 6, 12, 24, 36, and 48 hours, while in Group B (fentanyl group) the values were 4.07, 4.07, 4.02, 3.95, 3.85, 3.80, 3.575, 3.42, 3.02, 2.20, and the median values were 3.00, 3.00, 2.00, 2.00, 2.00, 2.00, 1.0, 1.0, 1.0 in Group A and 4.00, 4.00, 4.00, 4.00, 4.00, 3.0, 3.0, 2.0 in Group B. The VAS score in Group A was substantially lower than that of Group B (P < 0.0001).

Consequently, Group A required significantly less tramadol for top-up analgesia than Group B. Stress-related metabolites were measured in each group in the Grossi et al. study [10], which compared postoperative pain, stress response, and quality of life in patients undergoing minimally invasive

versus standard sternotomy coronary bypass surgery. The minimally invasive group showed significantly lower levels of these metabolites (P = 0.005). We assessed S. cortisol levels in both groups in our study, and on POD1, we discovered that the S. cortisol level was greater in the fentanyl group. The two groups' mean differences, however, did not vary statistically significantly.

According to a research by Khalil et al. [11], the SAPB group's mean arterial pressure did not significantly alter. In our investigation, we discovered that after 10 hours postoperatively, Group A's mean pulse rate (PR) was much lower than Group B's. The fentanyl group's mean SBP and DBP readings were noticeably higher. According to the research done by Bainbridge et al. [12], all patients who had thoracotomies had a drop in pO₂, with the biggest drop occurring during the first two postoperative days and a gradual restoration to preoperative levels after that.

In contrast to the SAPB group, the fentanyl group in our study had a substantial decrease in pO₂ after 10 hours and carbon dioxide (CO₂) retention beginning the second postoperative hour. Thoracotomy may result in a significant decline in postoperative pulmonary function, according to Richardson et al. [13], and the choice of pain treatment has significant consequences.

All thoracic units should require spirometry monitoring since it is necessary for an unbiased evaluation of the effectiveness of various pain management techniques. The spirometry conducted by the two groups in our study did not differ statistically significantly; nevertheless, patients in the SAPB group were able to do spirometry with a larger volume starting in the first hour, and patients in the fentanyl group starting in the fourth hour. Based on the results of chest X-rays, a research by Moghadam and Mohammad poor [14] showed that 47.5% of patients had acquired atelectasis following thoracotomy. We discovered that following surgery, basal atelectasis frequently occurred. In our POD0 trial, no patients in the SAPB group experienced mild basal atelectasis ($P < 0.001$), but 95% of patients in the fentanyl group did. The early recovery and shorter hospital stay that are goals of the ERAS recommendations are made possible by opioid sparing anaesthesia procedures. The SAPB group in our research had a mean ICU stay of 3.7 days, whereas the fentanyl group had a mean stay of 5.0 days. These differences were statistically significant ($P < 0.0001$).

In our investigation, we discovered that the SAPB group's VAS score was considerably lower than the fentanyl group's. The SAPB group's hemodynamic parameters—SBP, DBP, PR, and SpO₂—were steady. The SAPB group's POD1 stress response, measured by S. cortisol level, was lower. Group A required a significantly lower amount of top-up analgesic than Group B. The incidence of CO₂ retention was decreased in the SAPB group of patients. In the first 24 hours following surgery, it was noticeably greater in the fentanyl group than in the SAPB group.

Although the prevalence of hypoxemia was not statistically significant in either group, the SAPB group had relatively higher pO₂ levels after 24 hours compared to the fentanyl group. Up until 12 hours after surgery, patients in the SAPB group performed spirometry more accurately than those in the fentanyl group; beyond that, there was no statistically significant difference between the two groups' results. When comparing the SAPB group to the fentanyl group, the postoperative chest X-ray revealed a noticeable improvement. Early patient mobilization and release are facilitated by the considerably shorter ICU stay in the SAPB group compared to the fentanyl group.

Limitation of study:

There are some restrictions on our research. Due to scheduling and logistical issues, the sample size was restricted to a reasonable 80 cases.

A more reputable and empirically tested research with a bigger sample size may have approached the problem. It would be ideal to carry out a

comparable study over a somewhat longer time frame. The research employs an observational approach, and to improve validity and extrapolation, randomized trials are required.

Conclusion

For the purpose of managing postoperative pain, SAPB is therefore more effective in MICS patients than fentanyl. Additionally, it somewhat lessens the stress response, reduced cortisol levels and aids in chest physical therapy, which enhances overall chest compliance and promotes early ambulation, which shortens hospital stays and early departure. In addition, it takes less time, is safe, and has less hemodynamic problems.

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